

Plasmonic dimers in a solution: A theoretical approach to the optical activity in an ensemble of randomly oriented chiral and achiral plasmonic dimers: Effect of the coupling and scattering direction

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Abstract. We study the optical activity (OA) in an ensemble of randomly oriented chiral and achiral plasmonic dimers by summing the optical activity parameter (γ) over all possible orientations and we observe the following properties:

- If the geometry is achiral there exists orientations with $\gamma \neq 0$, but the ensemble sum over all possible orientations is zero ($\sum_{achiral} \gamma = 0$). There is no net OA in an ensemble of dimers if the geometry is achiral.
- If the geometry is chiral, for forward scattering γ depends on the coupling between the nanorods for all orientations of a single dimer and $\sum_{chiral} \gamma \neq 0$ for an ensemble of dimers with coupled nanorods. But, if there is no coupling between the nanorods, there is no OA in an ensemble of dimers with chiral geometry. Chiral geometry does not warrant OA in an ensemble for forward scattering.
- For scattering in the transverse directions with coupled nanorods the situation is similar to the forward scattering, but now there are terms that do not depend on the coupling coefficient in the expression of γ for an arbitrarily oriented dimer. Therefore, metasurfaces formed by selecting certain orientations with uncoupled nanorods can exhibit OA for scattering in the transverse directions.

Definition of the optical activity parameter for a single dimer with arbitrary geometry and orientation

Before studying the optical activity in an ensemble of plasmonic dimers (dimers in a solution) we have to define an optical activity parameter for a single dimer in an arbitrary geometry and random orientation in 3D space. Consider the dimer given in Fig.1. In order to express the most general geometry and orientation we begin with two arbitrary unit vectors \mathbf{m} and \mathbf{n} separated by a third vector \mathbf{r} . Unit vectors represent oriented dipoles associated with the nanorods located at positions \mathbf{r}_m and \mathbf{r}_n , where $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_m - \mathbf{r}_n$. If \mathbf{m} , \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{r} lie in the same plane ($\mathbf{m} \times \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{r} = 0$) the geometry is achiral, otherwise chiral.

Figure 1. Randomly oriented dimer of general geometry. Unit vectors \mathbf{m} and \mathbf{n} represent oriented dipoles (nanorods) located at points \mathbf{r}_n and \mathbf{r}_m .

When the geometry of a dimer is given, it is possible to define the plasmonic coupling between the nanorods by means of the dyadic Green function and calculate the far field components of the induced dipoles under a given external electromagnetic excitation. Then it is straightforward to calculate the scattering matrix (Jones matrix) of the dimer to show that the optical activity response of a physical system is related to the asymmetry in the Jones matrix [1], [2]:

$$\gamma = i(J_{12} - J_{21}). \quad (1)$$

γ is the complex anisotropy parameter associated with the circular anisotropy of the optical element, J_{12} and J_{21} are the anti-diagonal elements of the Jones matrix.

Next, we consider an ensemble of randomly oriented dimers. We assume that all dimers in the ensemble have the same geometry and they are not coupled with each other, but there may be an interaction (coupling) between the nanorods of each dimer.

In this work, in our theoretical expressions and BEM simulations we calculate the sum of γ over a large number of random orientations and we define the ensemble average of γ :

$$\bar{\gamma} = \frac{\sum \gamma}{N} \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of random orientations or the number of dimers in the ensemble. It is also useful to calculate $\sum |\gamma|$, because, in some cases $\sum |\gamma|$ may not be zero even though $\sum \gamma$ vanishes because of the symmetry.

Optical activity in an ensemble of chiral dimers for forward scattering

We calculate the far field components of the scattered electric fields and we derive the Jones matrix for forward scattering (scattering in the z axis) for an arbitrary dimer geometry and orientation by using the generalized matrix method given in the Appendix. Then, we calculate the γ_z parameter associated with a single dimer:

$$\gamma_z = -2\mu\alpha\delta(n_x m_y - n_y m_x) \sin(kr_z) \quad (3)$$

- m_i and n_i are the components of the unit vectors \mathbf{m} and \mathbf{n} that represent the orientations of the nanorods (Fig. 1).
- $k = 2\pi/\lambda_R$, λ_R is the localized surface plasmon resonance wavelength of each nanorod, α is the Lorentzian (scalar) polarizability, r_z is the z component of the vector \mathbf{r} between the nanorods. In our calculations we keep the excitation energy constant, hence α is just a complex constant number.
- δ is the coupling coefficient which is a function of the distance D between the nanorods ($D = |\mathbf{r}|$). δ contains a phase term, e^{ikD} , μ is the overall coefficient ($\mu = \varepsilon\alpha/(1 - (\alpha\delta)^2)$). Quadratic form of the denominator of μ is responsible for the plasmon hybridization for strong coupling.
- μ , α and δ do not depend on the orientation of the dimer.

We restrict our calculations to an ensemble of dimers with orthogonal nanorods (Fig. 2), but the results are more general. We simulate our formula for γ_z (Eq.3) by generating randomly oriented orthogonal dimers. In order to define the orientations of the dimers we generate two random unit vectors \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} , then we calculate the cross product of them which results in a new unit vector \mathbf{z} ($\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{v}$), and we apply the matrix form of a quaternion rotation twice about the \mathbf{z} -axis on \mathbf{u} (or \mathbf{v}) to generate the orthogonal unit vectors \mathbf{m} and \mathbf{n} in the \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v} plane. Finally, we write the separation between the nanorods as

$$\mathbf{r} = \frac{D}{\sqrt{3}}(\mathbf{m} - \mathbf{n} + \mathbf{z}). \quad (4)$$

We keep the excitation energy constant. In the geometry given in Fig.2 we let $X = Y = Z = d$ ($d = D/\sqrt{3}$) for simplicity and we investigate the OA response of the ensemble of randomly oriented dimers by summing γ_z over large number of random iterations.

- We calculate $\sum_{chiral} \gamma_z$ for different values of d . Coupling between the nanorods decreases with increasing distance d . For small values of d there is a peak, but $\sum_{chiral} \gamma_z$ quickly diminishes with increasing separation. For large d , where there is no coupling between the nanorods, $\sum_{chiral} \gamma_z = 0$. This is an immediate result of Eq.3, because if $\delta \rightarrow 0$, $\gamma_z \rightarrow 0$, for all orientations. In this uncoupled region $\sum_{chiral} \gamma_z$ oscillates with an interference like pattern.

BEM simulations verify our formula simulations (Fig. 3). By means of iterated simulations with gold rectangular nanorods of length=100 nm, height=width=10 nm we calculate $\sum \gamma_z$ and $\sum |\gamma_z|$ by summing over different orientations and we repeat the calculations for different separations between the nanorods. In the simulations we systematically rotate the dimers to cover all possible orientations by successively applying three different rotation matrices to perform three rotations, first about the x and y axes and then about the new z axis.

Figure 2. A chiral geometry of a plasmonic orthogonal dimer. \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{m} represent nanorods located at points $\mathbf{r}_n = (0, Y, 0)^T$ and $\mathbf{r}_m = (X, 0, Z)^T$. For simplicity we let $X = Y = Z = d, D = \sqrt{3}d$. Plane wave excitation is along the \mathbf{k} vector.

Figure 3. Chiral geometry and forward scattering. BEM simulations of sum of γ_z over orientations that generated by rotation matrices as a function of distance d . $\sum \gamma_z \rightarrow 0$ for large d for forward scattering (Left figure). $\sum_{chiral} |\gamma_z| \rightarrow 0$ as $d \gg 400$ nm because of the diminishing coupling (Right figure).

Achiral geometry for forward scattering

If we let $Z = 0$ in the dimer configuration given in Fig.2 the geometry is achiral by definition, $\mathbf{r} = \frac{D}{\sqrt{3}}(\mathbf{m} - \mathbf{n})$, but $r_z \neq 0$ for some orientations, hence, for coupled nanorods, according to Eq.3 $\gamma_z \neq 0$ in general, but the ensemble sum is zero, $\sum_{achiral} \gamma_z = 0$. Because of the symmetry, for each orientation there exists another orientation that cancels γ_z of its counterpart. However, this is true only for an ideal ensemble. Since $\sum_{achiral} |\gamma_z| \neq 0$ for coupled nanorods with small d (Fig. 4), we may observe OA in an ensemble of limited

number of dimers (nonideal ensemble). For the same reason it is possible to construct metasurfaces of achiral dimers that exhibit OA by selecting orientations with $\gamma_z \neq 0$.

Figure 4. Achiral geometry and forward scattering. BEM simulations for an ensemble of dimers in achiral geometry ($Z = 0, D = \sqrt{2}d$). Plane wave excitation is along the \mathbf{k} vector and the scattered fields are calculated along the z -axis (forward scattering). $\sum_{achiral} \gamma_z = 0$ for all d (left figure), $\sum_{achiral} |\gamma_z| \rightarrow 0$ for uncoupled nanorods (right figure).

Optical activity in an ensemble of chiral dimers for transverse scattering directions

We also study scattering of light by an ensemble of chiral and achiral dimers in the x -axis. Derivation of the γ_x parameter for a single dimer in an arbitrary geometry and orientation can be found in the Appendix:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \gamma_x = & -i\mu n_y(n_x + n_z)e^{-ik(r_z-r_x)/2} \\
 & -i\mu m_y(m_x + m_z)e^{ik(r_z-r_x)/2} \\
 & -i\mu\alpha\delta(n_z m_y + n_y m_x)e^{ik(r_z+r_x)/2} \\
 & -i\mu\alpha\delta(m_z n_y + m_y n_x)e^{-ik(r_z+r_x)/2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

We write γ_x as a sum of two terms, $\gamma_x = \gamma_{x_1} + \gamma_{x_2}$:

$$\gamma_{x_1} = -i\mu(n_y(n_x + n_z)e^{-ik(r_z-r_x)/2} + m_y(m_x + m_z)e^{ik(r_z-r_x)/2}) \tag{6}$$

$$\gamma_{x_2} = -i\mu\alpha\delta((n_z m_y + n_y m_x)e^{ik(r_z+r_x)/2} + (m_z n_y + m_y n_x)e^{-ik(r_z+r_x)/2}) \tag{7}$$

γ_{x_1} does not contain δ , i.e., it does not depend on the coupling between the nanorods. Values of α and δ should be taken into account in order to estimate the relative

magnitude of γ_{x_1} with respect to γ_{x_2} . Magnitude of γ_{x_1} is very small as compared to γ_{x_2} for coupled nanorods. However, if we focus on dimers with uncoupled nanorods, we observe that the effect of the coupling independent term (γ_{x_1}) becomes important in $\sum |\gamma_x|$. This explains why we may have a giant optical activity for certain orientations of dimers with uncoupled nanorods for scattering in the x -axis [4].

Results of the iterated BEM simulations with chiral dimers for scattering in the x -axis is given in Fig.5. $\sum_{chiral} \gamma_x$ decreases with decreasing coupling, but $\sum_{chiral} |\gamma_x|$ remains constant even for uncoupled nanorods, this is due to the coupling independent term, γ_{x_1} . Therefore, in contrast to the forward scattering, $OA \neq 0$ for certain orientations of chiral dimers formed by uncoupled nanorods.

Figure 5. BEM simulations for an ensemble of chiral dimers with scattering in the x -axis. Sum of γ_x is calculated over different orientations for different values of d (Left figure). $\sum_{chiral} |\gamma_x|$ is almost constant even for very large distances between the nanorods due to the coupling independent term in γ_x (Right figure).

Achiral geometry for transverse scattering

If the geometry is achiral, $\sum_{achiral} \gamma_x = 0$ even for an ensemble of dimers with coupled nanorods (Fig.6). Because of the symmetry for each orientation there exists another orientation that cancels that of its counterpart. But $\sum_{achiral} |\gamma_x| \neq 0$. This is due to the orientations for which $\gamma_x \neq 0$ and this is true even for dimers with uncoupled nanorods. Therefore, metasurfaces formed by achiral dimers with certain geometry and orientations can exhibit giant OA for scattering directions other than the forward scattering.

Figure 6. BEM simulations with achiral dimers for scattering in the x -axis.

Optical activity in an ensemble of chiral dimers for backscattering

For scattering in the $-z$ direction (backscattering) we define a new coordinate system x', y' for the backscattering Jones matrix. In order to calculate the backscattering Jones matrix we define the scattered fields in the new coordinate system:

$$P'_{nx} = -e^{-ikr_z/2}P_{nx}, \quad P'_{mx} = -e^{ikr_z/2}P_{mx}, \quad P'_{ny} = e^{-ikr_z/2}P_{ny}, \quad P'_{my} = e^{ikr_z/2}P_{my}. \quad (8)$$

From Eq.(8) and Eqs.(21)-(24) we calculate γ_{-z} :

$$\gamma_{-z} = -2i\varepsilon\alpha\mu[n_x n_y e^{-ikr_z} + m_x m_y e^{ikr_z} + (n_x m_y + m_x n_y)\alpha\delta] \quad (9)$$

In Eq.(9) we have a term that does not depend on δ and we have $\gamma_{-z} \neq 0$ for some orientations of dimers with coupled and uncoupled nanorods; hence, $\sum_{chiral} |\gamma_{-z}| \neq 0$ for any d as in the case of the scattering in the x -axis; but, $\sum_{chiral} \gamma_{-z} \approx 0$ for dimers with coupled and uncoupled nanorods (Fig.7). For a backscattering with achiral individual dimers and a random ensemble of them the situation is very similar to the case with scattering in the x -axis.

Appendix

We begin with a general geometry of plasmonic nanorods that constitute a dimer in three-dimensional space to study the emergence of optical activity in an ensemble of randomly oriented chiral and achiral dimer configurations.

We define 3D Jones matrices \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{N} that correspond to unit vectors \mathbf{m} and \mathbf{n}

Figure 7. BEM simulations for backscattering with chiral dimers

Figure 8. BEM simulations for backscattering with achiral dimers

(Fig. 1):

$$\mathbf{M} = \alpha_m \begin{pmatrix} m_x m_x & m_x m_y & m_x m_z \\ m_y m_x & m_y m_y & m_y m_z \\ m_z m_x & m_z m_y & m_z m_z \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{N} = \alpha_n \begin{pmatrix} n_x n_x & n_x n_y & n_x n_z \\ n_y n_x & n_y n_y & n_y n_z \\ n_z n_x & n_z n_y & n_z n_z \end{pmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

where α_m and α_n are the Lorentzian polarizabilities associated with the nanorods. In the following we assume that $\alpha_m = \alpha_n = \alpha$ and nanorods can be polarized only along their long axes. We choose a plane wave excitation in the x - y plane.

When we put two nanorods close to each other we have to consider mutual interactions. Each one of the induced dipoles experiences the field of the other dipole and this coupling effect should be taken into account to find the actual dipole of each nanorod [3]:

$$\mathbf{P}_m = \mathbf{M}(\varepsilon\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}_m) + k^2\bar{\bar{\mathbf{G}}}(\mathbf{r})\mathbf{P}_n), \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_n = \mathbf{N}(\varepsilon\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}_n) + k^2\bar{\bar{\mathbf{G}}}(\mathbf{r})\mathbf{P}_m), \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{P}_m and \mathbf{P}_n are the induced electric dipole moments, \mathbf{r} is the space vector between the nanorods, $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}_m)$ and $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}_n)$ are the excitation fields at the dipole positions, $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{G}}}(\mathbf{r})$ is the free-space electric dyadic Green's function. The effect of $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{G}}}(\mathbf{r})$ on \mathbf{P} is defined as

$$\bar{\bar{\mathbf{G}}}(\mathbf{r})\mathbf{P} = (A + B\bar{\mathbf{u}})\mathbf{P}, \quad (13)$$

$\bar{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{u}\mathbf{u}^T$, \mathbf{u} is the unit position vector between the particles along \mathbf{r} , and

$$A = \left(1 + \frac{i}{kD} - \frac{1}{k^2D^2}\right)g(D), \quad (14)$$

$$B = \left(-1 - \frac{3i}{kD} + \frac{3}{k^2D^2}\right)g(D), \quad (15)$$

$g(D) = e^{ikD}/4\pi D$ ($D = |\mathbf{r}|$).

Eqs. 11 and 12 generate 6 coupled equations to be solved; but they immediately reduce to 2 coupled equations because \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{N} are of rank one matrices and components of \mathbf{P}_m (\mathbf{P}_n) are proportional to each other. For example, if $n_x, m_x \neq 0$:

$$P_{ny} = \frac{n_y}{n_x}P_{nx}, \quad P_{nz} = \frac{n_z}{n_x}P_{nx}; \quad P_{my} = \frac{m_y}{m_x}P_{mx}, \quad P_{mz} = \frac{m_z}{m_x}P_{mx}. \quad (16)$$

We solve only two coupled equations to find P_{nx} and P_{mx} under plane wave illuminations, $\mathbf{E}_n = e^{-ikr_z/2}(E_x, E_y, 0)^T$ and $\mathbf{E}_m = e^{ikr_z/2}(E_x, E_y, 0)^T$, where we assume that \mathbf{n} is behind \mathbf{m} as viewed in the z -axis:

$$P_{nx} = \varepsilon\alpha n_x e^{-ikr_z/2}(n_x E_x + n_y E_y) + \frac{n_x}{m_x}\alpha\delta P_{mx}, \quad (17)$$

$$P_{mx} = \varepsilon\alpha m_x e^{ikr_z/2}(m_x E_x + m_y E_y) + \frac{m_x}{n_x}\alpha\delta P_{nx}. \quad (18)$$

$\delta = k^2((\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{m})A + (\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{u})(\mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{u})B)$. We solve the coupled Equations (17) and (18):

$$P_{nx} = \mu n_x [e^{-ikr_z/2}(n_x E_x + n_y E_y) + e^{ikr_z/2}(m_x E_x + m_y E_y)\alpha\delta], \quad (19)$$

$$P_{mx} = \mu m_x [e^{ikr_z/2}(m_x E_x + m_y E_y) + e^{-ikr_z/2}(n_x E_x + n_y E_y)\alpha\delta], \quad (20)$$

where $\mu = \varepsilon\alpha/(1 - (\alpha\delta)^2)$. Quadratic form of the denominator of μ suggests two peaks in the spectra of the components of \mathbf{P}_n and \mathbf{P}_m that correspond to two hybridized energies [3].

We rearrange the terms:

$$P_{nx} = \mu n_x [(e^{-ikr_z/2}n_x + e^{ikr_z/2}m_x\alpha\delta)E_x + (e^{-ikr_z/2}n_y + e^{ikr_z/2}m_y\alpha\delta)E_y], \quad (21)$$

$$P_{mx} = \mu m_x [(e^{ikr_z/2} m_x + e^{-ikr_z/2} n_x \alpha \delta) E_x + (e^{ikr_z/2} m_y + e^{-ikr_z/2} n_y \alpha \delta) E_y], \quad (22)$$

Similarly, we write P_{ny} and P_{my} :

$$P_{ny} = \mu n_y [(e^{-ikr_z/2} n_x + e^{ikr_z/2} m_x \alpha \delta) E_x + (e^{-ikr_z/2} n_y + e^{ikr_z/2} m_y \alpha \delta) E_y], \quad (23)$$

$$P_{my} = \mu m_y [(e^{ikr_z/2} m_x + e^{-ikr_z/2} n_x \alpha \delta) E_x + (e^{ikr_z/2} m_y + e^{-ikr_z/2} n_y \alpha \delta) E_y], \quad (24)$$

We write the far field components P'_{ni}, P'_{mi} at the detector point for forward scattering:

$$P'_{nx} = e^{ikr_z/2} P_{nx}, \quad P'_{mx} = e^{-ikr_z/2} P_{mx}, \quad P'_{ny} = e^{ikr_z/2} P_{ny}, \quad P'_{my} = e^{-ikr_z/2} P_{my}. \quad (25)$$

Now, it is straightforward to write the elements of the associated Jones matrix for forward scattering:

$$J_{11} = \mu(n_x n_x + m_x m_x + 2n_x m_x \cos(kr_z) \alpha \delta) \quad (26)$$

$$J_{12} = \mu(n_x n_y + m_x m_y + n_x m_y e^{ikr_z} \alpha \delta + m_x n_y e^{-ikr_z} \alpha \delta) \quad (27)$$

$$J_{21} = \mu(n_x n_y + m_x m_y + n_x m_y e^{-ikr_z} \alpha \delta + m_x n_y e^{ikr_z} \alpha \delta) \quad (28)$$

$$J_{22} = \mu(n_y n_y + m_y m_y + 2n_y m_y \cos(kr_z) \alpha \delta) \quad (29)$$

Previously, we have defined a parameter (γ) that corresponds to the circular anisotropy of the system [1]:

$$\gamma = i(J_{12} - J_{21}) \quad (30)$$

Hence, the γ parameter of a single dimer for forward scattering is

$$\gamma_z = -2\mu\alpha\delta(n_x m_y - m_x n_y) \sin(kr_z), \quad (31)$$

where $(n_x m_y - m_x n_y) = (\mathbf{m} \times \mathbf{n})_z$.

It is worth noting that there are terms that do not depend on the coupling coefficient (δ) in J_{12} and J_{21} but they cancel out when we calculate γ_z . Therefore, γ_z depends on the coupling coefficient for every orientation and it goes to zero as $\delta \rightarrow 0$ for large separations. This means that, in an ensemble of randomly oriented uncoupled dimers we cannot observe OA even if the geometry of each dimer is chiral.

On the other hand situation is different for other scattering directions. As an example we study the chiral response of the system for scattering in the x -axis:

$$P_{nx'} = -e^{ir_x/2} P_{nz}, \quad P_{mx'} = -e^{-ir_x/2} P_{mz}, \quad P_{ny'} = e^{ir_x/2} P_{ny}, \quad P_{my'} = e^{-ir_x/2} P_{my}. \quad (32)$$

Here we assume that \mathbf{n} is behind \mathbf{m} as viewed in the x -axis and $-z$ axis now corresponds to the new x axis (x'), then γ_z reads as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_x = & -i\mu n_y (n_x + n_z) e^{-ik(r_z - r_x)/2} \\ & -i\mu m_y (m_x + m_z) e^{ik(r_z - r_x)/2} \\ & -i\mu\alpha\delta (n_z m_y + n_y m_x) e^{ik(r_z + r_x)/2} \\ & -i\mu\alpha\delta (m_z n_y + m_y n_x) e^{-ik(r_z + r_x)/2} \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

We may write γ_x as a sum of two terms:

$$\gamma_{x1} = -i\mu(n_y(n_x + n_z)e^{-ik(r_z-r_x)/2} + m_y(m_x + m_z)e^{ik(r_z-r_x)/2}), \quad (34)$$

$$\gamma_{x2} = -i\mu\alpha\delta((n_zm_y + n_ym_x)e^{ik(r_z+r_x)/2} + (m_zn_y + m_yn_x)e^{-ik(r_z+r_x)/2}), \quad (35)$$

where γ_{x1} does not depend on δ and α .

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- [2] Instead of γ one may suggest to study the circular dichroic response of the system. Let $\Delta I = I_{RCP} - I_{LCP}$, I_{RCP} and I_{LCP} are the scattered intensities that correspond to illuminations with left and right handed circularly polarized light. Theoretically, it can be shown that $\Delta I = \tau \mathbf{Re}(\gamma) + \mathbf{Im}(\alpha\beta^*)$, where τ, α, β and γ are basic anisotropy parameters that given in [1]. The second term is not related with the circular anisotropy of the system, and in this expression we do not have the imaginary part of γ that corresponds to the circular birefringence, for this reason we use γ as a measure of optical activity.
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